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**WHY THE FACIAL PROFILE BECAME A SOURCE OF COMPLEXES IN
THE 21ST CENTURY**

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Annotation:

In the 21st century, the side profile of the face has become one of the main sources of dissatisfaction with appearance. As The Independent (2025) notes, a sculpted, defined jawline has turned into the "new holy grail of beauty" thanks to social media, video calls, and filters. The main reason is the so-called "hidden epidemic of small

jaws." In the book *Jaws: The Story of a Hidden Epidemic* by Sandra Kahn and Paul Ehrlich (2018) and in a Stanford University review published in *BioScience* (2020), it is shown that over the last 150 years human jaws have shrunk by 10–15% due to soft ultra-processed food, mouth breathing, and poor posture. As a result, the lower jaw moves backward, creating a "recessed" or "sloping" profile and often a double chin.

The Guardian (2025) confirms: the modern diet, especially the trend of feeding children soft foods and the widespread shift to ultra-processed products, disrupts the natural development of the face in children and teenagers. In the past, people rarely noticed their side profile. Today it is constantly compared to the perfect ideal seen on phone screens every day.

Keywords:

, Jaws epidemic, Ultra-processed food, Mouth breathing, Side profile, Jawline, Recessed chin, Looksmaxing, Mewing ,Soft food ,Appearance complex ,Profile insecurity ,Fear of side profile ,Comparison with ideal

Introduction

Over the past 20 years, with the emergence and popularization of social networks and gadgets, the social practices of modern people have changed significantly. Every day, spending time on social media and seeing the faces of models under filters or after plastic surgeries, many people, without realizing it, push themselves into a state of depression, acquiring complexes about their facial features and especially their profile.

The main reason for this phenomenon is the radical change in the perception of appearance under the influence of digital technologies. The front camera of a smartphone and platform algorithms emphasize the side silhouette: hashtags #sideprofile and #jawlinechallenge gain millions of views. Filters and editors create a single "Instagram face" — with a sharp jawline, a pointed chin, and harmonious proportions. A real face in profile often looks "recessed" or "weak" compared to this ideal, significantly reinforcing complexes.

The second, no less important reason is biological in nature. Over the last 150 years, the jaws of modern humans have shrunk by an average of 10–15%. The cause lies not in genetics, but in a radical change in lifestyle. Key factors include the transition of infants to artificial feeding, as well as the widespread consumption of soft or ultra-processed food instead of hard food. An example is feeding children porridge-like dishes or soft fruits instead of naturally firm food. As a result, the jawbones and muscles do not receive sufficient stimulation for growth, because the blood supply to these structures is not stimulated adequately. The stimulus for growth is the process of chewing, in which the masticatory muscles actively work: the lateral and medial pterygoid muscles (*Musculus pterygoideus lateralis et medialis*), the masseter muscle (*M. masseter*), and the temporal muscle (*M. temporalis*).

This ultimately leads to insufficient growth of the lower and upper jaws, as a result of which the face acquires a recessive ("sloping") profile. These morphological changes are accompanied by the appearance of a nasal hump (due to the descent of the upper part of the face), breathing problems (including obstructive sleep apnea) due to the narrowing of the upper airways. Among the aesthetic and functional consequences are dental crowding, various types of malocclusion, as well as a double chin even in individuals with normal body weight. The latter is associated with insufficient lower jaw size, causing the skin and soft tissues to visually sag.

These biological changes have coincided with the explosive growth of social networks. Whereas in the last century, only a few people saw a person's side profile, today it has become a public "filter" of attractiveness. Young people aged 18–35 are particularly acutely aware of the discrepancy with their digital ideal. Studies show that 70–80% of teenagers experience dissatisfaction with their appearance precisely because of constant comparison on the internet. Psychologists note that the brain perceives such comparison as a threat to social status, leading to increased anxiety, refusal of photographs, and even avoidance of social contacts.

Discussion

In our time, due to modern eating habits and lifestyle, young people increasingly experience malocclusions, dental crowding, and facial asymmetry. These problems can persist for many years and significantly affect quality of life.

Seeking solutions, many, without suspecting it, become victims of social media trends. A vivid example is the so-called "Instagram face" and looksmxing — an aesthetic featuring clearly defined, "sharp" cheekbones, hollow cheeks, and the absence of a double chin. People actively promoting this appearance are called

looksmaxers. They share various techniques on social media: gua sha for the cheekbones, special expanders and jaw exercisers for developing the masticatory muscles, breathing exclusively through the nose, pressing the tongue against the hard palate (mewing), and avoiding soft, sweet, and salty foods in favor of hard ones. Undoubtedly, some of these recommendations have a rational basis and can be beneficial. However, one must not forget that facial shape and bite condition are primarily influenced by genetics, body fat percentage, general physical activity, posture, and harmful habits (such as mouth breathing in childhood).

Conclusion

It is important to understand: independent experiments with jaw exercisers or strict diets are not always safe and can lead to temporomandibular joint disorders, increased tooth wear, or even worsening of the bite. Therefore, any changes in the myofunctional balance are best carried out under the supervision of a dentist or orthodontist.

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